

The impact of inclusive cultures

on improving democratic coexistence in schools

Impacto de las culturas inclusivas en la mejora de la convivencia democrática escolar

Hernández Domínguez Pablo Ysidoro¹ Magíster en Gestión Pública, MBA en Innovación Pedagógica y Gestión de Centros Educativos. Licenciado en Educación. Correo: phernandez1@ucvvirtual.edu.pe Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9735-1936>

Sánchez Díaz Sebastián² Doctor en Educación. Magister en Educación – Especialidad Matemáticas. Docente de Investigación, con el manejo de software del SPSS. Correo: ssanchez@ucv.edu.pe Orcid: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0099-7694>

Muñoz Ledesma Sabino³ Postdoctorado en Ciencias. Doctor en Educación. Magíster en Docencia Universitaria y Gestión Educativa. Autor del libro Metodología de la Investigación Científica, Ed. 1ª - 4ª. Correo: smunoz@ucv.edu.pe <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6629-7802>
Universidad César Vallejo, Perú

¹Autor principal y contacto directo del manuscrito. Correo: phernandez1@ucvvirtual.edu.pe

Fecha de consignación de manuscrito: 01-02-2023

Fuente de financiamiento: Universidad César Vallejo, Perú

Conflicto de intereses: Los autores del presente artículo científico manifiestan NO tener ningún conflicto de intereses.

Expresiones de gratitud: A la Universidad César Vallejo, Perú por su apoyo a la ciencia y tecnología.

Received: 10/26/2022 Accepted: 01/15/2023 Published: 02/12/2023 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7926193>

Abstract

It is a challenge for educational institutions in Peru to respond effectively to the pedagogical, ethical-training, humanistic and interdisciplinary requirements and challenges that an inclusive quality education demands, especially in a post-pandemic context. The objective was to find out the impact of inclusive cultures on the improvement of democratic school coexistence in the reality of Peruvian Regular Basic Education. Regarding the methodology, a theoretical-reflective review was carried out in the scientific databases of Scopus, Scielo and Redalyc, using the method of analysis-synthesis. The results showed that the practice of inclusive cultures has a significant impact on the strengthening and consolidation of democratic school coexistence. It is concluded that the school community must be more than willing to contribute to the consolidation of an accessible, accessible, adaptable and acceptable educational ecosystem of diversity, with greater attention to students with special educational needs.

Keywords: Social integration, school integration, democratization, inclusive education

Resumen

Es un reto para las instituciones educativas del Perú responder con eficacia a los requerimientos y desafíos pedagógicos, ético – formativos, humanísticos e interdisciplinarios que demanda una educación inclusiva de calidad, tanto más en un contexto post – pandémico. Se tuvo por objetivo conocer el impacto de las culturas inclusivas en la mejora de la convivencia democrática escolar en la realidad de la Educación Básica Regular peruana. Referente a la metodología, se realizó una revisión teórica – reflexiva en las bases científicas de datos de Scopus, Scielo y Redalyc, empleando el método del análisis – síntesis. Los resultados evidenciaron que la práctica de culturas inclusivas posee impacto significativo en el fortalecimiento y consolidación de la convivencia democrática escolar. Se concluye que la comunidad escolar debe estar más que dispuesta a contribuir al afianzamiento de un ecosistema educativo accesible, asequible, adaptable y aceptable de la diversidad, con mayor atención a estudiantes con necesidades educativas especiales.

Palabras clave: Integración social, integración escolar, democratización, inclusión educativa

During their stay in Regular Basic Education (RBE), students may be susceptible to adopting certain types of negative behaviour patterns as a result of an improper formation, development, and consolidation of inclusive cultures (IC), which are essential for a proper coexistence in various social scenarios, starting with the first of them: the family. Being able to interact in society not only implies the adoption of rules and compliance with these, but also being aware of the importance of being able to generate a new perspective on the importance of educational inclusion (EI). In this maelstrom, certain types of pedagogical strategies that are anachronistic for the current problems are called into question; this is why there is a need to significantly reformulate educational policies, requiring them to be more coherent with the reality of each social stratum²; the role of the school in training future citizens and members of a society often conflicted by intolerance and unwillingness to accept human diversity leading to peaceful coexistence cannot be overlooked³. In this framework, good coexistence should not only be understood as the absence of conflict, but as an edifying part of a new society in which it is necessary to work on values related to empathy and conflict management through dialogue and agreement in the school slogan of the development of good educational practices⁸. The power to promote IC alludes to the need to be receptive in its different modalities, starting with a change of perception with regard to inclusivity, moving away from the term disability, given that its purpose is to show inclusion as part of good coexistence¹⁶. In this aspect, the effectiveness of this precept is highlighted in order to spread within the school a mutual cooperation based on inclusiveness and where each member is important for its human essentiality, mega-diverse, and with edifying values for a better coexistence¹¹. It is necessary to contribute to the consolidation of good school coexistence through Peruvian inter-sectoral educational management based on: The creation of a Specialised Educational Service (SES) that can execute a suitable praxis in the selection of teacher profiles with expertise in special educational needs (SEN); realisation of strategic alliances with community servants and application of public management knowledge to the field of education¹². A strategy for the impact of good IC in the democratic coexistence in schools (DCS) is the joint adoption of a socio-constructivist praxis-oriented not only to achievements, but also to the significant learning that parents, tutors, and teachers will obtain regarding inclusion, being transcendental that the teaching performance in the pedagogical strengthening in the classroom and in the school, community has a positive impact on the educational society⁹. Based on what has been described in this theoretical review, the aim was to compile various scientific sources on the cardinal objective of the study, which in this case was to compile information on the impact of IC on the improvement of the DCS. In this way, this article shows a summary of all this with the aim of contributing to the continuous study of the varied information on this subject, providing various managers and teachers with multiple plans to increase and consolidate the praxis of DCS, making a holistic differentiation of the anachronistic and amphibological pedagogy; In

this way, school management in diverse RBE populations will be more competent in the practice of good IC that establishes a DCS based on empathy and the common good of academic knowledge - training of future fellow citizens; in this aspect, it is necessary to have the capacity for good decision making for insertion in a society that requires greater consideration of educational diversity, which should not be treated with hostility, but as an opportunity to include vulnerable sectors that are often forgotten by governance¹³. This hostility and rejection of inclusion only highlight the urgent need for schools to take coordinated action against segregation, neglect, exclusion, devaluation, and indifference suffered by students with SEN, all the more so when inclusive and flexible educational systems are required for diversity⁵. Knowledge and implementation of such actions could have been extremely useful during the Covid 19 pandemic, where students with some kinds of disability were 49% more likely to have no school attendance and, in turn, 42% less likely to obtain a basic knowledge of the school curriculum.

Method

A review of the literature was carried out with the intention of systematising the epistemological bases on IC and its impact on DCS as pedagogical knowledge that will make it possible to improve educational inclusion in relation to functional interculturality. In virtue of this, the method of analysis-synthesis was used, taking into account that this method makes it possible for diverse knowledge to be linked together and to understand a problem in its varied configuration¹; in this perspective, the review article pursues a scientific - humanistic objective that goes beyond compiling and analysing diverse academic information, in view of the fact that it produces key knowledge for future research in the framework of science and technology, in such a way as to guarantee the evolution of the diverse academic areas of a society that needs to be nourished with solid epistemological foundations¹⁵. In order to obtain the scientific data, an advanced and systematised search of scientific studies was carried out, selecting a total of 19 references from freely accessible journals that are indexed in the Scopus, Scielo, and Redalyc databases, published in the last four years, using the following search terms: "Educative inclusion" and "Democratic school coexistence" in the subject field; likewise, a resolution of the Ministry of Education of Peru¹⁴ inherent to the variables of the research were selected. The importance of scientific rigour in the selection of inclusive content and motivation was also emphasised with the intention that such knowledge should be reproducible for science and technology¹⁹. The scientific literary production was obtained during the months of August 2022 until the second week of December of the same year, in Spanish, English, and Portuguese, inherent to the field of education and directly related to the area of Personal Development, Citizenship, and Civics. By virtue of the above, it was prioritised that the compilation of this scientific literature should have thematic nuclei relevant to inclusion and democracy, guaranteeing its effectiveness in the development of this research²¹.

Results

In reference to the area of Personal Development, Citizenship, and Civics, its curricular importance was highlighted on the basis of the following evidence: It induces students to adopt rules of conduct oriented towards tolerance, mutual respect, empathy, defense of human rights, and equity in order to create new school societies whose main guideline is to solve problems through dialogue and consensus for the common good; it promotes the participation of students in the implementation of the School Coexistence Plan; as for the academic coordination of the area, it urges this office to create school coexistence teams, whose professionals must be proficient in the resolution of school conflicts related to educational inclusion^{2,5}. In this context, it is imperative to highlight the work of teachers in a critical context such as a pandemic health emergency, and that the school as a whole made efforts so that the DCS in virtual environments can be worked on in a way that focuses on the needs of students and the importance of their role in the educational society, with greater importance when dealing with socio-cultural contexts of inequality and where transdisciplinary teaching work has to be carried out, obtaining important knowledge from other sciences^{10,6}. The actions of school and society must have a common goal: to promote good IC practices in order to make social interactions with people with SEN as edifying as possible; in this context, although it is true that the school is in the role of carrying out good actions to promote and strengthen IC, such behaviours should be carried out even after the student's stay in RBE; based on the above, the dissemination of social communication, tolerance and respect for human diversity will be a real test to check if the scale of inclusive values (IV) has been worked on in a relevant way^{19,7}. The school should work in a transdisciplinary way on the self-regulation of emotions and ethical reasoning in different situations of coexistence in society¹¹.

Discussion

Through the analysis, the importance of the area of Personal Development, Citizenship, and Civics as it relates to DCS and the significant effect of IC practices in the context of a school that does not see inclusion as a barrier, but as an opportunity for schoolchildren to have better conditions to be valued according to their diversity, has been re-evaluated. This mission is not simple, much less achievable in the short term, due to the fact that one barrier to overcome is the flexibility for the creation of an inclusive curriculum^{5,13}; however, it is not possible to avoid the transcendence of attention to school diversity; accordingly, the teaching praxis must be heterogeneous and not traditional, because the latter is based on retrograde and classist models, of little use in the educational system, discrediting its direct insertion of cross-cutting approaches in the various academic areas¹⁸; in another sense, curricular experiences should be based on the preparation of students to face different obstacles in order to coexist well; in this aspect, coordinated and collegial work with families is required²⁰, with a greater focus on valuing the student as a unique and unre-

peatable being, respecting his or her dignity. This intentionality must be based on a reevaluation of the person and the right to social justice for the vindication of such citizens in the educational community, so that everyone can and has the right to opportunities that allow them to reflect perceptible improvements at a behavioural and humanistic level, above all in the acceptance of human diversity⁹; in this slogan, it was established that an indicator of social justice is those actions that result in lasting peace and that all educational actors are able to maintain it in the areas of equity, interculturality, and orientation towards the common good³. Condensing the data analysed and contrasted in this research, it is plausible to identify that the various limitations that are contrary to the impact of IC on good DCS should not only refer to the achievement of IE indicators but also to the ethical-formative formation of RBE students, This is why they should be based on a cooperative, gender-equitable and interdisciplinary approach in the collegiate work of the teaching, administrative and educational support staff, since it is essential that school management provides opportunities for their implementation^{17,18}. The present study showed that IC have a significant impact on the strengthening and consolidation of DCS, taking into account that any educational society needs to be based on the continuous practice of IV; therefore, the school and its human capital must be more than willing to provide a school ecosystem accessible to students with SEN, without any kind of stigmatisation of students or teachers. In sum, it is recommended to carry out experimental and/or quasi-experimental studies relevant to the variables of this research where the benefits of educational engineering for the differentiated attention of students with SEN are applied.

Conclusions

First, there is a positive impact of IC on DCS, therefore, the school as a whole has the opportunity to be part of an educational environment where respect for educational diversity and interaction with students with SEN takes place within the framework of ethics, inclusion, and democracy so that all students can achieve satisfactory levels of attainment. Second, teachers and tutors, when carrying out their pedagogical function, must understand that they not only transmit knowledge, but that they are also bearers of IV, intercultural, democratic, and ethical-formative values of significant transcendence to students in favour of future citizens who are accessible to educational and human diversity. Third, it is the duty of Peruvian governance to carry out and implement public policies inherent to EI, involving the various regulatory bodies of RBE in Peru and providing training and development opportunities for educational human talent. Fourth, the creation of school communities must be based on the continuous practice of IV, the basis of a school that is open, flexible and tolerant of diversity. Fifth, it is necessary to implement intervention workshops on inclusive education, where the educational community is made aware of the importance of a school for all based on inclusion and attention to diversity.

Referencias

1. Alina I, Somano KQ, Alberto C, León M. métodos teóricos de investigación: Análisis- Síntesis, Inducción - Deducción, Abstracto - Concreto e Histórico - Lógico. ResearGate. 2020 Dec 1;1(Modelos teóricos de investigación): 978–959. Disponible en: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/347987929>
2. Ascorra P, Cuadros O, Cárdenas K, García-Meneses J. Autopercepción de la gestión de la convivencia escolar en sostenedores públicos chilenos. *Psicoperspectivas* [Internet]. 2020; 19(1):1-13. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5027/psicoperspectivas-vol19-issue1-fulltext-1827>
3. Ascorra P, Cárdenas Mancilla K, Gálvez P, Ávila A, González C, López V. Relación entre estilos de convivencia e indicadores de desarrollo personal y social en escuelas chilenas. *Rev Psicol* [Internet]. 2021; 30(2):1-14. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5354/0719-0581.2021.57840>
4. Booth Booth T, Ainscow M. Index for inclusion developing learning and participation in schools Tony Booth and Mel Ainscow editing and production for CSIE Mark Vaughan Published by the Centre for Studies on Inclusive Education (CSIE). 2002.
5. Carbajal Padilla P, Fierro Evans MC. Convivencia Escolar: Una revisión del concepto. *Psicoperspectivas* [Internet]. 2019; 18(1):1-19. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5027/psicoperspectivas-vol18-issue1-fulltext-1486>
6. Correa Silva M, da Silva J. Educação, desigualdade e proteção social. *Rev O Social em Questão* [Internet]. 2021; 52(1):131–154. Disponible en: <https://www.maxwell.vrac.puc-rio.br/56408/56408.PDF>
7. Diez M, Universidad de la República, de Pena L, Uruguay, Universidad de la República; Uruguay. La escuela ante el fracaso escolar en contextos de inequidad: entre mandatos sociales y respuestas medicalizadas. *Prax Educ* [Internet]. 2022; 26(1):1–18. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.19137/praxiseducativa-2022-260116>
8. Escola J. Comunicação Educativa: perspectivas e desafios com a COVID-19. *Educ Real* [Internet]. 2020; 45(4):1-21. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/2175-6236109345>
9. Fortoul-Ollivier CF-E/. “MEJORAR LA CONVIVENCIA” Una relectura analítica de experiencias innovadoras en escuelas latinoamericanas. *Rev Invest* [Internet]. 2021; 15-45. Disponible en: <https://www.scielo.org.mx/pdf/rmie/v27n92/1405-6666-rmie-27-92-15.pdf>
10. Flores Chaupis A. Actitudes transdisciplinarias de los docentes y logros educativos en Educación Secundaria en Huánuco. *Rev Estud Exp Educ* [Internet]. 2022 [citado 2023 febrero 3]; 21(45):209–31. Disponible en: https://www.scielo.cl/scielo.php?pid=S0718-51622022000100209&script=sci_arttext
11. Leigh González CA, Leigh González E, Gómez Zuloaga S. Aplicación de la Escala de Afrontamiento Frente a Riesgos Extremos en el profesorado de preescolar en Chile en el contexto de emergencias masivas: estudio de caso. *Rev Educ* [Internet]. 2021;1–17. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.15517/revedu.v46i1.43853>
12. Libardoni dos Santos JO, Teixeira Sadim GP, Schmidt C, De Souza Matos MA. O atendimento educacional especializado para os educandos com autismo na rede municipal de Manaus-AM. *Rev Bras Estud Pedagóg* [Internet]. 2021; 102(260):99 - 119. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.24109/2176-6681.rbep.102.i260.4150>
13. Martínez JMA. Pandemia y convivencia escolar: incertidumbres y retos. *Tópicos Educacionais* [Internet]. 2021; 27(1):1-21. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.51359/2448-0215.2021.250402>
14. Ministerio de Educación. Lineamientos de Tutoría y Orientación Educativa para Educación Básica [Internet]. 2021. Disponible en: <https://cdn.www.gob.pe/uploads/document/file/1439330/RVM%20N%C2%B0%20212-2020-MINEDU.pdf.pdf>
15. Nassi-Calò L. El papel de los artículos de revisión va más allá de sintetizar el conocimiento actual sobre un tema de investigación [Internet]. *SciELO en Perspectiva*. 2021 [citado el 7 de febrero de 2023]. Disponible en: <https://blog.scielo.org/es/2021/07/14/el-papel-de-los-articulos-de-revision-va-mas-alla-de-sintetizar-el-conocimiento-actual-sobre-un-tema-de-investigacion/>
16. Ocampo González A. Epistemología de la educación inclusiva. *Revista Colombiana de Ciencias Sociales* [Internet]. 2021; 12(2):439-452. Disponible en: <https://doi.org/10.21501/22161201.4066>
17. Ortiz-Mallegas S, López V. Condiciones de organización del trabajo en convivencia escolar y cooperación profesional. *Rev Estud Exp Educ* [Internet]. 2021; 20(42):183–98. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21703/rexe.2021204ortiz-mallegas11>
19. Silva LFC da, Berto Pucca M. Produtividade científica e tecnológica dos docentes da Universidade Federal de Roraima. *Aval Rev Aval Educ Super (Camp)* [Internet]. 2022; 27(2):388–408. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/s1414-40772022000200010>
20. Sousa FRS, Sousa LS, Carvalho H de S, Silveira FM da. Formação docente na perspectiva da educação antirracista como prática social. *Práx Educ* [Internet]. 2022; 17:1–16. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5212/praxeduc.v.17.19366.039>
21. von-Zeschau JF, Sánchez-Mosquera M. Conselhos econômicos e sociais. Uma revisão da literatura com foco em sua eficácia e avaliação. *Rev adm pública* [Internet]. 2022; 56(4):465–487. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/0034-761220220033>

